

UNIFIED USER EXPERIENCE MODEL ENABLING A MORE COMPREHENSIVE UNDERSTANDING OF EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Design deals with improving the lives of people. As such interactions with products, interfaces, and systems should facilitate not only usable and practical concerns but also mediate emotionally meaningful experiences. This paper presents an integrated and comprehensive model of experience, labeled 'Unified User Experience Model', covering the most prominent perspectives from across the design field. It is intended to support designers from different disciplines to consider the complexity of user experience. The vision of the model is to support both the analysis of existing products, interfaces, and systems, as well as the development of new designs that take into account this complexity. In essence, we hope the model can enable designers to develop more marketable, appropriate, and enhanced products to improve experiences and ultimately the lives of people.

KEYWORDS: *Emotional Design, User Experience, UX, Unified User Experience Model*

INTRODUCTION

At its core the field of design is about creating a better life for people. As such interactions with products, devices, and interfaces should facilitate and mediate emotionally meaningful experiences so as to positively impact people's lives. User experience (UX) is understood in different ways by several disciplines (Roto et al. 2011); however there are common fundamental principles. Beyond usability, a point of interest in science and industry for many years, the recent approach of UX extends the view on user product interaction to include aspects of emotions (Green & Jordan, 2002; Hummels, 2000; Manzari, 2003). Therefore, the motivation of UX is about enhancing the overall experience to meet psychological and emotional needs, including the motives of the user (Hassenzahl, 2010). Further, by triggering the user's emotions it is more likely that this will increase brand loyalty and help create a point of difference for products in saturated markets.

The Complexity of Experiences

Experiences are situated in real life and need to be considered from this perspective, and due to their nature are complex, contextual, evolving, dynamic, short and long-term, and deal with the issue of time. It is relevant therefore that any conceptual model takes into account these aspects and attempts to acknowledge the complexity of UX.

In this paper we propose an integrated and comprehensive model of experience covering the most prominent perspec-

tives from across the design field. It is intended to support designers from different disciplines to consider and deal with the user experience. The vision is for the model, labeled 'Unified User Experience Model', to support both the analysis of existing products, interfaces, and systems as well as the development of new designs that take into account this complexity. In essence we hope the model can enable designers to develop more marketable, appropriate and enhanced products, and systems to improve experiences and ultimately the lives of people.

STATE OF THE ART

In order to develop an integrated model on UX we need to provide an overview on the state of the art models on user experience and emotional design. We divide them into two categories: models describing individual UX aspects and foundational principles (Norman, 2004; Desmet, 2002; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Jordan, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2010), and others describing UX as a process which includes multiple influences and is inherently more complex (Khalid & Helander, 2008; Karapanos et al., 2009; von Saucken et al., 2012; von Saucken et al., 2013b; Gomez, 2012; Gomez et al., 2013). Furthermore, we divide UX into a Micro and Macro perspective, which includes aspects from most of the models presented and contextualizes the user experience as a dynamic activity. Finally, we derive a unified approach that covers the relevant and important aspects for experience design synthesis.

Models Describing Fundamental UX Aspects

Presented here are prominent models on user experience and emotional design, including Norman's (2004) *Three levels of processing*, Desmet's (2002) *Basic model of product emotion*, Desmet & Hekkert's (2007) *Framework of product experience*, Jordan's (2000) *Four pleasures framework*, and Hassenzahl's (2012) *Three level hierarchy of goals*. They all focus on individual experience aspects and do not claim to regard UX holistically. This way, they are descriptive and support the foundational aspects of UX.

Processing Experiences by Norman (2004)

Norman (2004) details distinctive processing layers that cause different kinds of experiences including *visceral*, *behavioral*, and *reflective*. Norman posits that a product is perceived and automatically assessed through its look and feel (visceral), as well as its purpose and functionality (behavioral), leading to an action. Above these, the reflective level represents conscious thought and reflection of that experience (Figure 1).

- **Visceral level.** This is the fastest system of processing and makes rapid judgments and assessments of the perceived appearance and beauty of objects and the environment. Visceral design may relate to the shape, materials, colors, feel, sound, and smell of a product: the embodied design.
- **Behavioral level.** Deals with pleasure and effectiveness of use related to usability and functionality: What does a product do? What function does it perform? For experienced users this level of processing is performed almost unconsciously.
- **Reflective level.** When it comes to rationalizing the product interaction, it is the reflective level that is being engaged. Users think consciously about their products — about their stories, self-image, and pride. This processing is not aroused directly by sensory input, but is based on the memory of behavioral experience, and is highly dependent on the user's unique background (culture, values) and history (remembrance of experiences).

Figure 1. Three levels of processing by Norman (2004)

Product Emotions by Desmet (2002)

One of the earliest emotional experience models was the *Basic Model of Product Emotions* by Desmet (2002), consisting of four parameters in the eliciting process of emotions including appraisal, concern, product, and emotion (figure 2).

This model is based on the proposition that all emotional reactions result from a process in which individuals appraise the product as harmful or beneficial (Frijda, 1986). 'Appraisal' refers to the immediate and automatic evaluation of an event in which both individual concern and product interaction have an impact. 'Concern' relates to the significance or value that an individual places on any given experience. According to Frijda (1986), events that satisfy a concern yield positive emotions, while events that threaten a concern lead to negative emotions. The 'product' is the mediator and influences the overall appraisal by facilitating or threatening a concern. Desmet argues that the dynamic of all three parameters; appraisal, concern, and product, lead to an *emotional* reaction.

Product Experience Patterns by Desmet and Hekkert (2007)

With their *Framework of Product Experience*, Desmet & Hekkert (2007) present three different experience patterns that help designers 'design for experience'. They distinguish between aesthetic experience, experience of meaning, and the emotional experience attributed to a user-product interaction (Figure 3).

The 'aesthetic experience' pattern is triggered by the product's sensory impact on the user — the perceptual process. A product can be pleasant in terms of optic (beautiful to look at), acoustic (pleasant sound), haptic (good to touch), or olfactory (smells nice). The pattern relating to the subjective user's interpretation, labeled 'experience of meaning' pattern is based on memory retrieval and association of a product — the cognitive process. The experience of meaning depends on the individual and the cultural context of the user. When it comes to evaluation (appraisal) of product perception and cognition, an *emotional experience* can be triggered — an affective phenomenon.

Figure 2. Basic model of product emotions by Desmet (2002)

Figure 3. Framework of Product Experience by Desmet & Hekkert (2007)

Figure 4. Three level hierarchy of goals by Hassenzahl (2010)

Four Pleasures by Jordan (2000)

In *Designing Pleasurable Products*, Jordan (2000) argues that usability-based approaches are ‘limited, even dehumanizing’, as the user interacting is regarded only with ‘cognitive and physical characteristics’. He presents the *Four Pleasures Framework* to expand this perspective and include psychological aspects in order to understand users more realistically. Jordan distinguishes between four types of pleasure in his classification:

- **Physio-pleasure.** The body and sensory organs, like tactile and olfactory stimuli, trigger this experience. A designer aiming at creating physio-pleasure needs to design surfaces, shapes, smells, and further embodiment characteristics according to the physical and physiological needs of the user.
- **Socio-pleasure.** This experience is triggered by relationships with other persons or society as a whole: a product facilitates social interactions — people want to feel a sense of belonging and social interaction.
- **Psycho-pleasure.** Psycho-pleasure experiences pertain to people’s cognitive and emotional reactions — they want to achieve certain goals and be proud. This experience is triggered by the judgment of process effectiveness and the results of a product interaction based on the user’s expectation. To achieve this, designers need to develop usable, efficient, and effective products that make users feel competent.
- **Ideo-Pleasure.** This experience is based on moral or ethical values, and personal aspirations, and how these are met by product interaction. The product can illustrate certain values through its physical appearance (e.g. sustainable materials for eco-design), but also the intangible brand image of a product.

Goals and Needs by Hassenzahl (2010)

For Hassenzahl (2010) the fulfillment of goals is a central issue of his book *Experience Design*. He distinguishes between three levels of goals based on Activity Theory by Kaptelinin & Nardi (2006) (Figure 4).

- **Lowest level: motor-goals.** On this level the goal and actions are more concrete with regard to a specific product: *How* does a user fulfill a goal? Different products thereby cause different motor-goals for the same do-goal: ‘making a call’ with a mobile phone, demands other operations than with the Skype application.
- **Middle level: do-goals.** This level of goals is labeled as the what-question: *What* does a user want to achieve? It is a concrete desired outcome of an action, independent from a concrete product or technology. For example, the do-goal of ‘making a call’ can be achieved by using a telephone or Skype.
- **Top level: be-goals.** This is the level that targets experiences: *Why* does a user want to achieve a goal? It relates to rather abstract user needs common for all humans. This is the level to start from when designing for experiences: asking what are the be-goals for the user and design based on those needs.

In order to design experiences starting with be-goals, Hassenzahl relates to a set of ten basic user needs, originally defined by Sheldon et al. (2001): autonomy, competence, relatedness, self-actualizing, security, luxury, popularity, physical thriving, self-esteem, and pleasure. He proposes bringing these needs into the interaction context and to derive product concepts fulfilling them.

Models Describing UX as Process

In contrast with the first section, the following models are more complex and describe user experience as the interplay of different influences over time. The framework by Khalid and Helander (2006) describes the evaluation of affective design from the designer and user perspective. Karapanos et al. (2009) focus on the change of user experience over time. *The Customer Experience Interaction Model* by von Saucken et al. (2012) integrates different discipline perspectives and theories on UX.

Figure 5. Framework for evaluation of affective design by Khalid & Helander (2006)

Framework for Evaluation of Affective Design by Khalid and Helander (2006)

A useful framework is outlined by Khalid & Helander (2006), labeled 'Framework for Evaluation of Affective Design' (Figure 5). This framework is descriptive and intends to outline issues that must be addressed in order to illustrate affective design from the *Designer's Environment* (left) and the *Affective User Experience* (right).

Within the designer's space three constraints exist including artifact design elements, context of use, and the social dimension. Artifact design elements refer to Norman's visceral, behavioral, and reflective characteristics that products will elicit during interaction (Norman, 2004). The context of use refers to the physical environment and situations in which the designer expects the user to interact with the product. Finally, the issue of trends, fashion, and social and cultural norms needs to be considered. For the user, individual user needs as well as the cognitive and affective systems will influence the emotional evaluation. Khalid & Helander surmise that users employ cognitive and affective channels to evaluate designs. The user's individual characteristics, like culture, propensity for creativity, and other attributes impact both cognitive and emotional evaluative channels.

Temporality of Experience by Karapanos et al. (2009)

Karapanos et al. (2009) proposed the 'Temporality of Experience' model (figure 6). Following the work of Silverston & Haddon (1996), Karapanos et al. identified three phases of product adoption including orientation, incorporation, and identification, which are driven by motivating forces including increasing familiarity, functional dependency, and emotional attachment that transition users from one phase to the next.

There is an initial stage identified as *Anticipation*, which results from the expectations prior to any physical experience

Figure 6. Temporality of experience by Karapanos et al. (2009)

with a device. *Orientation* refers to the initial experiences with the device, like the initial learning curve or excitement with new features. *Incorporation* reflects the stage when the device becomes more meaningful in the users' lives. During this stage, usability and usefulness become significant factors that impact experience. Finally the *Identification* phase ushers in acceptance of the device into the cultural and social fabric of life, communicating self-identity and serving to differentiate or connect to others.

Customer Experience Interaction Model CEIM by von Saucken et al. (2012)

The first integrated model we discuss is the *Customer Experience Interaction Model* (CEIM), by von Saucken et al. (2012). It provides a holistic view on the interaction of users with products. CEIM incorporates different relevant models and views from the disciplines of engineering, human factors, industrial design, and psychology. It supports the communication between developers by creating a common terminology (Figure 7).

CEIM is based on the ‘Block Diagram of Human Machine System’ by Schmidtke (1993) representing a classic ergonomics perspective with the goal to improve the working task fulfillment by adapting the machine, its interface, and the environment impact to the user’s capacity. It focuses the human machine interaction with relevant ports in between (sensory organs, muscular system, and user interface). Since user

experience requires a stronger consideration of the human perception and processing, CEIM details the user element by adding *emotions* and *motives*.

CEIM enlarges the functional understanding of products by *Indication, Aesthetic, and Symbolic* aspects according to Steffen (2000). User experience is more than just fulfilling tasks in a most efficient manner. The emotional value and experience by using an expensive sports car can be the result not only of great driving properties (practical function), but also of the pleasant exterior and interior design considering shape and materials (aesthetic function), as well as the prestige through product and brand (symbolic function).

Macro UX and Micro UX

Similar to the ‘Framework of Product Experience’ by Desmet & Hekkert (2007), we perceive in essence two different but integrated levels by which users experience products that we call *Macro* and *Micro UX*. We can observe experiences that are mainly driven by the context of use — by other people, brand values, culture, external influences, and so on, and we categorize this level as *Macro UX*. At this level the product is the enabler or mediator of its purpose and function, and the experience would not arise without the context. Those experiences are processed on the reflective and behavioral level (Norman, 2004) and relate mainly to psycho- and ideopleasures (Jordan, 2000). They are long-term experiences and fulfill be-goals (Hassenzahl, 2010).

In contrast, *Micro UX* is directly caused by the product interaction, and the corresponding product’s embodiment within the immediate environment of the user. These experiences correspond to Norman’s (2004) visceral level and cause aesthetic experiences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007), as well as relating to physio-pleasure (Jordan, 2000). These experiences are caused by the product’s embodiment, are generally experienced in a short amount of time and influence motor-goals

Figure 7. Customer Experience Interaction Model CEIM by von Saucken et al. (2012)

CRITERIA	MACRO UX	MICRO UX
UX approach	Creating a big picture of UX and deriving product concepts	Proposing UX improvement and avoiding UX violation in detail
User goals	Be-goals (why user wants it)	Motor-goals (how user uses it)
Relationship	User-Product-Context over time	User-Product interaction
Impacts	Evaluation of overall experience	Interaction
Starting point	Predefined set of user needs	Existing product design
Result	Effective UX	Efficient UX
Influence	Product concept and functions	Product embodiment design
Development phase	Early stage of goal setting	Embodiment design, optimization
Time span	Long-term: consideration during whole design process necessary	Short-term: occasional support during several stages possible
Abstraction level	Rather abstract (goals, purpose)	Concrete hints for design
Opportunity	Radical UX innovation	Only incremental UX innovation
Risk	High, changes entire product	Low, just improvement in detail

Table 1. Comparison of Macro UX and Micro UX by von Saucken et al. (2013a)

(Hassenzahl, 2010). The differences between Macro and Micro UX are outlined in Table 1. It is important to identify the differences between these two levels as they form the basis of the model presented in this paper. However, it is their integration and the way that both levels interact that is most relevant for understanding an authentic user experience.

UNIFYING TWO USER EXPERIENCE MODELS

We present a synthesis of two models of user experience developed by the authors (Figures 8 and 9) in an attempt to conceptualize the complexity of the user experience. Firstly, von Saucken et al. (2013b) developed the *UXIM* as a refined version of the *CEIM* (Figure 7) presented earlier, which focused on the user-product interaction. The models are descriptive and mention context (physical and social for instance), but context is not further detailed or structured. This is where the *DE³* framework by Gomez (2012) is used to support the model developed by von Saucken et al., but is itself more predictive and thereby supports design synthesis. Through the unification of the two models, the *Unified User Experience Model* (Figure 10) is presented.

User Experience Interaction Model UXIM by von Saucken (2013b)

CEIM (Figure 7) was evaluated in several industrial and student projects with the task of supporting user experience (UX) design. UX aspects were missing and several opportunities for improvement were defined:

- A descriptive model needs to cover the *temporal* aspect of UX beyond the actual interaction: people can have an experience before their first encounter through expectations formed from existing experience of related technologies, brand, advertisements, or others' opinions. Similarly, indirect experience extends after usage through reflection on previous usage, or through changes in people's appraisals of use (Karapanos et al., 2009; Roto et al., 2011).
- The inner representation of the used product, or *mental model*, has a strong impact on UX. Users derive a men-

tal model from their observation of the product (Norman, 2004). This inner model need not necessarily be appropriate to what leads to confusion and frustration — a bad experience.

- UX focuses on triggering positive user emotions. These *emotions* need to be considered stronger than in CEIM. A differentiation between rational and emotional perception before, during, and after the interaction would offer a new perspective on the human perception and judgment of products.
- CEIM illustrates many relevant aspects of UX, but it is difficult to determine where exactly *User Experience* arises. The model gathers many different perspectives, but is difficult to explain to people without previous knowledge. Furthermore, the illustration is text-based. A model should be more figurative and thereby intuitively understood.

We enriched CEIM with these insights to develop the 'User Experience Interaction Model' (UXIM) (Figure 8). It consists of three UX-relevant parts: the *interaction* of user and product (center, considering rational and emotional processing), the *temporal* perspective on the experience (left, expectation before usage and remembrance after usage), and the surrounding *environment* (right, including social influences and service systems). Additionally, we include the *mental model*, as it strongly influences the experience.

The illustrated user interacting with the product (represented by a laptop) takes the center stage. User and product are linked via a classic ergonomics cycle according to Schmidtke's (1993) ports: the user performs an action with the product using its input devices. The product carries out a function and returns the result via the output device. This is perceived and processed (interpreted) by the user leading to new actions. We included the enlarged function perspective of Steffen (2000) by adding the arrows *Aesthetics* and *Prestige*.

As UX is a subjective emotional reaction within the user, we get more into detail regarding the processing element: on the one hand, we distinguish between three time spans, represented by the cycle on the left side — before, during, and after usage (Roto et al., 2011). On the other, we divide the

Figure 8. User Experience Interaction Model UXIM by von Saucken et al. (2013b)

Figure 9. Designing for evolving emotional experiences (DE₃) framework by Gomez (2012)

processing element into a rational-driven cycle (the external ring), and an emotional-driven (the internal ring). We included a representation of a *mental model* in the center of the processing cycle.

Designing for Evolving Emotional Experiences Framework (DE₃) by Gomez (2012)

The framework ‘Designing for Evolving Emotional Experiences’ (DE₃) was developed by Gomez (2012) from a study exploring two types of portable interactive devices (PIDs), and provides some principles when considering emotional experiences at the Micro and Macro levels of the UX (Figure 9).

On the top far left is the title *Personal or Social context* (user-product interface in context), which relates to the Macro UX, or Norman’s (2004) reflective level, and Hassenzahl’s (2010) be-goals. Essentially, the model identifies that social interactions (social contexts) impacted the overall emotional experience to a large degree, varying slightly for each product category. Personal interactions (private contexts) did not impact the overall emotional experience to the same degree. Below that, on the bottom far left is the box explaining the findings relevant for the *User-product interface*, relating to the Micro UX, Norman’s (2004) visceral and behavioural levels, and Hassenzahl’s (2010) motor and do-goals. Principles for promoting positive experiences and avoiding negative experiences are provided as recommendations.

To promote positive UX, the following aspects with *Mediation* and *Functional* categories must be considered:

- **Mediation:** From the outset consider how the device will mediate (facilitate) experiences beyond the functional.
- **Functional:** Make certain that the device performs its core function well.

To avoid negative UX the following aspects regarding *Features* and *Auxiliary* categories must be considered:

- **Features:** Reduce the number of additional features on the device.
- **Auxiliary:** Consider creating service for auxiliary (tertiary) activities of the device.

Overall the DE₃ framework attempts to combine the Micro and Macro levels to form a holistic relationship and provide relevant recommendations. The DE₃ model is designed to enable designers, and design researchers, to conceptualise and frame the design of devices to promote positive emotional experiences, and reduce negative emotional experiences, at the Micro and the Macro UX level.

The Unified User Experience Model

The UXIM and DE₃ presented above (Figures 8 and 9), enriched with some of the principles and concepts of the models and frameworks presented earlier, were amalgamated into the *Unified User Experience Model* (Figure 10). The model aims to capture the complex, dynamic, evolving aspect of the experience over time. It is composed of both Micro and Macro UX level, which is argued to be a critical component for user experience.

The *Unified User Experience Model* frames von Saucken et al.’s (2013b) UXIM model at the center of the user experience and situates a variety of concepts from Gomez’s (2012) DE₃ framework and the other models presented previously into the Micro and Macro UX. The model has been designed to be dynamic in nature by having the capacity to consider the model in different modes. Potentially, there are three modes that take into account the (a) user-product interaction, (b) user-product within the Micro UX context, and (c) user-product-Micro UX within the Macro UX context (Figure 11).

It is these various modes in combination that try and capture the complexity of the user and product interaction in context. Each mode can be understood separately but it is in considering the three collectively that provides a more holistic view of the user experience. The elements of the model can be explained based on the three layers described above.

- (a) **User-product interaction.** This is the same as the UXIM model presented earlier (Figure 8, von Saucken et al., 2013b). The three time spans: before, during, and after use, are present as the rational-driven cycle (external ring), and the emotional-driven cycle (internal ring). Representation of the user’s mental model is included within the processing cycle.

Figure 10. Unified User Experience Model (after Gomez, 2012; von Saucken et al., 2013b)

Figure 11. Three modes: (a) user-product interaction, (b) user-product within Micro UX and (c) user-product-Micro UX within Macro UX

(b) **User-product interaction within Micro UX.** Here the Micro level is introduced and pertains to the product interaction and the corresponding product's embodiment within the immediate environmental context of the user. These experiences correspond to Norman's (2004) visceral level and cause aesthetic experiences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) and relate to physio-pleasures (Jordan, 2000), caused by the product's design, influencing the motor-goals (Hassenzahl, 2010). The various elements include:

- **Co-existing Products.** Other products that impact the user-product interaction — for instance a computer mouse or external hard-drive when interacting with a personal computer.
- **Product Service.** The necessary services required for the product to function properly — for instance an electrical outlet to plug the personal computer into.

- **Persons / People.** Other persons who impact on the user-product interaction.
- **Physical Environment.** The immediate physical environment of the user-product interaction — for instance the physical room the personal computer is situated in.
- **Weather.** The immediate environmental climate impacting the user-product interaction — for instance, if the interaction is occurring outside, rain or other conditions may prohibit activity completely.
- **Light.** The available light, natural or artificial, that is available for the user-product interaction to occur.

It is proposed that the Micro UX level impacts the immediate interaction between user and product, and although it can lead to emotional experiences, these are short-lived and may not go on to impact the emotional experience in the long term.

(c) **User-product-Micro within Macro UX.** This mode takes into account the entire model and is conceptually where the product becomes an enabler or mediator of its purpose and function within a given context. Those experiences are processed on the reflective and behavioral level (Norman, 2004), and relate primarily to psycho, social, and ideo-pleasures (Jordan, 2000). They are rather long-term experiences and fulfill be-goals (Hassenzahl, 2010). The various elements identified include:

- **Supersystem.** Other products and services that are coordinated within an integrated service system
- **Brand.** The brand (and associated values) and its influence on the user's longer-term choices, decisions, and interactions with current and future products and services.
- **Social.** The social environment in which the user is interacting within — for instance, is the experience occurring at home, in the office, in public, etc.
- **Culture.** Any cultural context that impacts the user-product interaction — for instance different cultural values that may exist in other countries.
- **Values.** The user's personal moral and ethical values that impact their choices in a general way — for instance, is the user environmentally conscious?
- **Service.** Specific facilities offered by the product or company above and beyond the product's functions and features — for instance, an extended warranty service.
- **Time.** This deals with the fact that interactions occur over time and as such are constantly changing, morphing, and ultimately evolving during this period.

It is proposed that the Macro UX level influences interactions more generally and impacts the emotional experience in the long-term.

IMPLICATIONS FOR DESIGN

The *Unified User Experience Model* aims to better capture and represent the complex, dynamic, evolving aspect of the user experience over time. It is dynamic in nature and composed of both Micro and Macro UX levels, which are argued to be critical when conceptualizing the actual experience. It is hoped that the model will enable designers to better analyze existing designs and develop novel designs that comprehensively consider the full complexity of the user experience. The model takes into account some of the most relevant elements from the prominent models and frameworks available in the literature, and amalgamates two existing models; the UXIM model developed by von Saucken et al. (2013b), and the DE3 framework developed by Gomez (2012).

From the outset it is maintained that the model expands the current understanding of UX and sets the standard for capturing the full complexity of the actual user product interaction. Further, the model aims to enable designers from various fields to better examine existing products, interfaces,

and systems as well as assist designers to develop improved and novel designs that take into account a more comprehensive view of UX.

Future Study

The authors propose to conduct experiments analyzing the user-friendliness, usefulness, and effectiveness of the 'Unified User Experience Model', with designers concurrently in Australia and Germany, so as to mitigate any potential limitations. To begin with, the model will be analyzed with design students in both countries to see how well the model works with less experienced designers. Further, the model will be used by industry in Germany to investigate its effectiveness within the business world. Similarly, design professionals in Australia will examine its value within the industrial design discipline.

CONCLUSION

Design is about improving the life of people including making experiences with products, devices, and interfaces easy and usable as well as emotionally meaningful. User experience (UX) is understood in different ways by several disciplines. However, the motivation of UX is to enhance the overall experience and meet pragmatic, functional, as well as the psychological and emotional needs and motives of users (Hassenzahl, 2010). From a marketing perspective, by triggering the user's emotions and creating brand loyalty, UX can help differing products in saturated markets.

In this paper we propose an integrated and comprehensive model of experience covering the most prominent perspectives from across the design field. It can be argued that no model could ever encapsulate the true complexity and reality of individual human experience, yet the critical components that make up experiences such as context, dynamism, evolving, and time need to be incorporated into any framework that attempts to comprehensively consider the user product interaction. Nevertheless, we believe this model is a worthwhile attempt at capturing this complexity. It is intended to support designers from different disciplines in order to consider and deal with the complexity of UX. The vision is for the model, labeled 'Unified User Experience Model', to support both the analysis of existing products, interfaces, and systems as well as the development of new designs. In essence we hope the model can enable designers to develop more marketable, appropriate, and enhanced products to improve experiences, and ultimately the lives of people.

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